

CLINICAL AND CLASSIFICATION OF IMMUNOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF JUVENILE RHEUMATOID DISEASES OF STUDENTS IN TEACHING CLINICAL SCIENCES IN MEDICAL EDUCATION

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ANNOTATION

In the article, the clinic and classification of immunological aspects of juvenile rheumatoid arthritis, acute rheumatic disease, etiopathogenesis, classification, clinical signs, diagnostic criteria, comparative diagnosis, treatment methods, prevention, and the spread of rheumatism, immunological aspects and classification of students in the teaching of clinical sciences in digital medical education. Treatment methods of the disease, etiology and pathogenesis of the disease, and its connection with infectious factors are discussed.

Key words: Digital medical education, clinical signs, diagnostic criteria, comparative diagnosis, treatment methods, prevention, immunological aspects, infectious factors.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассмотрены клиника и классификация иммунологических аспектов ювенильного ревматоидного артрита, острого ревматического заболевания, этиопатогенеза, классификация, клинические признаки, критерии диагностики, сравнительная диагностика, методы лечения, профилактика и распространение ревматизма, иммунологические аспекты и классификация студентов. в преподавании клинических наук в цифровом медицинском образовании обсуждаются методы лечения заболевания, этиология и патогенез заболевания, его связь с инфекционными факторами.

Ключевые слова: Цифровое медицинское образование, клинические признаки, критерии диагностики, сравнительная диагностика, методы лечения, профилактика, иммунологические аспекты, инфекционные факторы.

Introduction Teaching clinical sciences in medical education methodically increases the quality of medical education, pays attention to quality medical education, implements clinical innovative technologies that allow methodical development of practical professional skills in a real medical environment, social and cultural development of medical workers, attention is being paid to the

development of methodical professional competencies in an inclusive prism, and scientific research. As a result of globalization and technological progress in the world, innovative strategies based on the digital transformation of medical education are being widely implemented. By integrating the educational process, improving the needs-based individual medical education trajectories, the infrastructure and technological resources that serve to develop the universal competencies, creative and critical thinking skills necessary for learning and working in future children's medical specialists are being supported.

This, in turn, allows to carry out effective work on the practical use of the medical-methodical possibilities of the implementation of collaborative and teaching models of clinical sciences. Further improvement of educational services in medical education, expansion of quality education opportunities, training of highly qualified personnel in accordance with the needs of medical organizations, introduction of a dual education model based on practice and medical education, in this regard, higher medical education priority tasks have been defined in terms of increasing the academic and innovative potential of the institutions. Fundamental development of the medical field in our country in 2020-2030, introduction of international standards in the field of medicine, improvement of personnel training and qualification improvement processes in the field of medicine by introducing the credit-module system, implementation of positive international experiences in the field of medical education, science, practice and innovation effective work is being carried out.

Immunological aspects. The pathological process that develops in patients with YRA has two stages. The development and manifestation of the exudative phase is based on microcirculation disorders and damage to synovial membrane cells. It helps to increase the permeability of cell membranes and increases the penetration of plasma proteins and a number of cellular elements into the joint. As a result of this reconstruction, chronic inflammation develops (second stage), manifested by mononuclear infiltration in the structures of the synovial membrane of joints and cartilage. The inflammatory process characteristic of YRA lasts for many years, it has the character of autoimmune inflammation. When studying the etiology of JRA, it was pointed out that behind the clinical variety of forms lies the polymorphism of 4 KLA haplotypes, which is probably associated with immune "defects" in the child's body with a disease-prone phenotype. Combines all forms of JRA, in which the main target organ is the structures of the joint apparatus and primarily the synovial membrane. The

hypothesis of molecular mimicry is based on the similarity of the shell structure of some microorganisms with HLA. Therefore, they are not recognized and destroyed in time by the immune system of the human body. The receptor hypothesis assumes that HLA can act as a receptor for some pathogenic microorganisms, facilitating their entry into the cell where the pathological process develops. Also discussed is the hypothesis that HLA can be modified by infectious agents, especially viruses, such as by direct insertion of the viral genome into the HLA gene or by RNA. Such HLA is recognized as foreign in the body and the immune response develops against them.

In recent years, the hypothesis of the presence of immune response genes (Ir-genes) localized in the D or DR loci, balanced with the 1ILA system, has been discussed. Ir-genes control the interaction of macrophages and lymphocytes in the immune response, as well as regulate the differentiation and functional activity of T-cells.

A characteristic feature of the immune status in active inflammation in children with various types of JRA is the involvement (to one degree or another) of almost all parts of the immune system. Immunopathological reactions directly related to articular syndrome can be conditionally distinguished, general, i.e. Systemic, rheumatoid syndrome (articular-visceral forms), level of activity and possibilities of development of the disease. There are attempts to study the immunological features of the most common clinical forms and variants of the course of JRA in children. In general, RA is an autoimmune disease, classically described as a pathological condition that develops when the regulation of physiological immune processes is disturbed, which leads to the appearance of cellular and humoral immune responses against the components of one's own tissues. causes structural and functional disorders in target organs. As an autoimmune disease, an important feature of JRA is the overproduction of autoantibodies directed against antigens present on self-labels, inside cells, or in the extracellular spaces of the human body. Autoantibodies can react with a wide range of molecules - cytoplasmic components, nucleus, cell membranes, serum proteins, hormones, enzymes. HLA, nucleic acids, phospholipids, steroids, etc. can act as autoantigens. The main properties of autoantibodies are cross-reactions and the formation of antigen-antibody complexes in the bloodstream. Antigen-antibody reactions are accompanied by the activation of proteins of the complement system, which is manifested by a decrease in its titer in the synovium, an increase in vascular permeability, and the release of hydrolytic enzymes, active oxygen radicals, arachidonic acid metabolites (supplier).

prostaglandins). Immunoglobulins and rheumatoid factor (RF) molecules gradually accumulate and accumulate in the surface layers of articular cartilage, which promotes proliferative processes and pannus formation in the synovial membrane. According to the systemic (articular-visceral) forms, clinical manifestations and morphology of classic YRA, it is considered systemic vasculitis. Flows with events of polyserositis and organ damage. In patients suffering from YRA, characteristics are determined at almost all stages of the body's immune response. They depend on the form and form of the disease. In general, the leading role of immunopathological mechanisms in the pathogenesis of JRA is considered to be proven. Particular interest remains in the presence of proteins in the acute phase of inflammation, in particular, in CRP. It is considered an early manifestation of JRA and, together with high levels of IL-6 and a number of lysosomal enzymes, is considered a prognostic factor (marker) of the progressive course and early development of the disease. Systemic osteoporosis. A special role in the diagnosis of YRA is given to the determination of RF in the blood serum and synovial fluid of patients.

RF is an immunoglobulin of the IgG or IgM class. In the presence of RF, the disease is considered seropositive. This is determined by a complement-dependent hemolytic test. The level of interest in the specific ethical communication of the immune system is related to the clinical activity of the process, which is manifested by the hyperproduction of IgG and IgA. During the exacerbation of the disease, Ig (G2 and IgC3) subfractions increase, and during the remission of the inflammatory process, the concentration of IgG3 and IgG4 increases more. IgE. Children with oligoarthritis associated with eye damage (uveitis) often have antinuclear antibodies (ANA). Antibodies to components of cells and connective tissues (type I and II collagen, synovial membrane extracts, cartilage, endothelium) are often detected. This is most typical for children with a systematic process. In the blood, there should be an increase in the number of plasma cells (absolute and relative) and B-cells, as well as an imbalance in the coordination of B- and T-cells and a low level of α - and β -interferons. It should be recognized as a characteristic of most children with JRA. The degree of these disorders is related to the activity and severity of inflammation.

During remission of the disease, the functional status of lymphocytes is restored. Changes in cellular immunity in patients with JRA are heterogeneous, reflecting the polymorphism of the pathogenesis of different forms of the disease. Systemic forms of JRA are characterized by impaired immunoregulation, which is not associated with a decrease in suppressive potential, but with the

activation of type 2 T-helper function. Perhaps there is a genetic determinism of the T-cell defect in these cases. It is manifested by their functional incapacity.

Discussion Recent studies have shown that in children, especially in systemic forms of JRA, there is a significant impairment of the migratory functions of effector cells, particularly polymorphonuclear leukocytes and mononuclear cells. In patients with JRA, their dysfunction is mainly manifested by a decrease in the activity of leukocyte chemotaxis (migration of leukocytes to the site of inflammation) and chemokinesis (migration stimulated by the C5 component of complement). The primary (genetic) defect and the immune system have a significant impact on the inflammatory process, immediately focusing on the timing of the process.

Clinic and classification The clinical appearance of JRA depends on many factors - the child's age, heredity, gender, the initial state of the immune system, his environmental conditions, features of the psycho-emotional state of life, attitude to children. Patient and close relatives of the disease, timely diagnosis, adequacy of therapy. It should be noted that in 80% of cases, JRA is a severe chronic disease with a recurrent and progressive course that sooner or later leads to disability. The main clinical manifestations of the disease are joint damage, specific eye damage, and a generalized rheumatoid syndrome characterized by fever, typical rheumatoid rash, polyserositis, and internal organ damage caused by systemic rheumatoid vasculitis.

Clinically, in the stage of acute synovitis, the child is concerned about joint pain and swelling, limits his mobility, and body temperature usually rises. Later, fibrosis of the capsule and fibrous adhesions in the joint develop. Epiphyses of bones are eroded and destroyed. This process usually progresses, and the further development of fibrosis leads to a change in the configuration of the joint, limiting its mobility and ankylosis.

One of the most uncomfortable variants of JRA in children. Renal involvement is considered in the process because diffuse GN (vasculitis) develops in the kidney, which progresses to renal amyloidosis. It continues with persistent proteinuria, which threatens the development of chronic renal failure. But during therapy, it is necessary to distinguish vasculitis in renal vessels from persistent hematuria and proteinuria, because many drugs of the main group have nephrotoxicity. Often, with the development of the process and the rapid loss of bone mineral density, with the development of general osteoporosis, the excretion of calcium salts increases. Urine, which is also accompanied by

isolated hematuria or its combination with other symptoms of urinary syndrome.

Monoligoarthritis in young children. Combined with eye damage due to uveitis or keratopathy. Only girls get sick. Arthritis has a slow course and a good prognosis. Its activity is related to changes in immunity. The timing of the onset of eye damage and arthritis is often different (sometimes the second syndrome develops years later). For a long time, the patient has isolated uveitis or only oligoarthritis.

Monooligoarthritis occurs mainly in boys. Damage to large joints is characteristic and in some cases combined with sacroiliitis. Usually sick children over 10 years old. This variant of JRA is associated with HLA-B27, so it is often thought to be the likely cause of ankylosing spondylitis, which is more common in adults. Often, such a change does not occur in children, and the course of the disease is completely benign.

Conclusion In addition to the most typical forms of JRA described above, which occur in approximately 80% of patients, there are also less specific variants. Its course, as a rule, is very favorable, after 3-5 years, 50% of children recover, or very rare relapses are noted without a clear progression of the process, which requires a review of the diagnosis years later. Pathogenetic heterogeneity, clinical polymorphism of JRA, as well as different variants of the nature and outcome of the disease led to the development of a new classification.

1. Rheumatoid arthritis, articular-visceral (systemic) form (with damage to the reticuloendothelial system, heart, serous membranes, blood vessels, eyes, urine, nervous and bronchopulmonary systems):

- a) with limited visceritis;
- b) Still's syndrome;
- c) allergic septic syndrome.

2. Rheumatoid arthritis, mainly in the articular form (with or without eye involvement):

- a) polyarthritis;
- b) oligoarthritis;
- c) monoarthritis.

3. Combined with rheumatoid arthritis:

- a) rheumatism;
- b) immunological characteristics of diffuse connective tissue diseases JRA RF test is positive (seropositive), RF test is negative (seronegative).

Process of the disease: rapidly progressive, slowly progressive, without significant progression. Level of activity: high (level III), medium (level II), low (level I) remission. X-ray stage.

Stage I: periarticular osteoporosis, effusion into the joint cavity, signs of compression of periarticular tissues.

II. stage, on the background of the same changes, narrowing of the joint space, one bone usura

II. stage: widespread osteoporosis, obvious osteochondral destruction, dislocations, subluxations, systemic bone dysplasia.

IV. stage of change I-III stage and ankylosis.

Functional capacity of the patient

1. Saved.

2. The condition of the musculoskeletal system is broken:

a) self-service ability is preserved;

b) the ability to provide self-service is partially lost

c) self-service ability is significantly lost.

3. Damaged, but condition of eyes or internal organs.

In conclusion, it should be said that the progressive functional disorders of the locomotor system are characterized by the presence of the dynamics of the process described above in the first year of the course of the disease. If these symptoms are present within 1.5 to 3 years from the onset of the disease, the course is called gradually progressive.

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